

Chemical Investigation of *Chenopodium ambrosioides*

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The essential oil of *Chenopodium ambrosioides* Linn. has been the subject of study since it is one of the most important anthelmintics besides its being useful for several other purposes.¹⁻³ Aritasone⁴, a saponin and sapogenin⁵ have been isolated from this plant. No significant work appears to have been done on the Indian species so far. In view of its importance it appeared of interest to carry out systematic chemical investigation of the local variety of the plant.

A golden yellow essential oil, obtained by steam distillation of the green shrub, possesses pungent and disagreeable odour (characteristic of the plant) and bitter taste. The oil has been found to contain mainly four components (T.L.C.) including *p*-cymene (CO—T.L.C.) as a significant constituent. It does not appear to contain any carbonyl compound, but contains phenolic constituents (17%). Properties of the oil have been studied by standard methods^{3,6} and compared with the oil obtained in foreign countries.

TABLE

	Local	American	Other foreign countries	
			A	B
Sp. gr.	0.8893/32°	0.937-0.990/25°	0.964/20°	0.981/20°
Sp. Rot.	0.09/32°	-4° to -12°	-53°	-0.20'
Ref. Index	1.476/32°	1.4741-1.4778/20°	1.4923/20°	1.4765/20°
Solubility, 70% alc. (vol.)	6-7 of 75%	2-10	0.8 of 80%	3-7
Yield (%)	0.37	1-2	—	0.29-0.51
Ascaridole content (%)	20.15	65-91	19.07	58-67

Air-dried plant material (4 Kg) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), for 18 hr. The brownish viscous extract (60 g.) was triturated with acetone and divided

into acetone-soluble and acetone-insoluble parts. The acetone-insoluble part (6 g.) on further purification gave almost colourless solid (2 g.) which on chromatography (alumina), elution with petroleum ether and benzene, and crystallisation yielded three products.

The petroleum ether eluates afforded colourless waxy substance (A—980 mg), crystallised from acetone-alcohol, m.p. 65–66°. This was examined by T.L.C. (Silica gel—Ag NO₃) and G.L.C. and found to contain mainly *n*- and branched-chain saturated hydrocarbons (C₂₁—C₃₁), traces of some olefins, and a mixture of esters of higher fatty acids and alcohols. The C₂₉ paraffin is present in largest amount.

The petroleum-benzene (3 : 1) eluate furnished a ketone (B—120 mg), crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 77–78°. This was identified as heptacosane-14-one giving positive carbonyl-group tests, (Found : C, 82.15; H, 13.83; calc. for C₂₇H₅₄O : C, 82.16; H, 13.79%), characteristic ir. peaks at 1725 cm⁻¹ (Ketone), 720, 730 cm⁻¹ (CH₂)_n.

The petroleum ether benzene (1 : 1) eluate yielded an alcohol (C—280 mg), crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 84–85°, (Found : C, 82.30; H, 13.72; calc. for C₃₀H₆₂O : C, 82.11; H, 14.24%). It gave characteristic ir. peaks at 3300, 3350 cm⁻¹ (OH); 720, 730 cm⁻¹ (CH₂)_n, acetate (by usual method) m.p. 67°. It was confirmed as triacontyl alcohol⁷.

The acetone-soluble oily fraction (50 g.) was saponified with alcoholic KOH (N/2, 200 ml). The unsaponifiable matter on trituration with methanol gave a colourless solid (300 mg.). On chromatography over alumina (10 g.), elution with petroleum ether and crystallisation (acetone-alcohol) a product (A₁—140 mg), m.p. 62–63°, was obtained. It was found (G.L.C.) to contain a mixture of open-chain saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons only. (See A).

Petrol-Benzene (1 : 1) furnished a product which was crystallized from methanol in shining crystals (m.p. 160°). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test, yellow colour with tetranitromethane, and showed characteristic i.r. peaks at 3300 cm⁻¹ (OH), and 1645 cm⁻¹ (C = C).

The mass spectrum analysis showed molecular ion peaks at 414, 412 (main) ; 399, and 397 etc. indicating it to be a mixture which on repeated chromatography (alumina) and crystallisation (methanol) yielded only one pure compound, m.p. 165°. It gave an acetate (m.p. 172°) by usual procedure and was identified as α -spinasterol (M⁺ 412).

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REFERENCES

- (a) 'Chopras Indigenous drugs of India', R. N. Chopra, I. C. Chopra, K. L. Handa and L. D. Kapoor, U. N. Dhur & Sons, Calcutta—1958, 100.
(b) 'The Wealth of India' (Raw materials), C.S.I.R., New Delhi, vol. II, C, 1950, 127.
- (a) L. D. Kapoor, K. L. Handa and I. C. Chopra, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12A, 311.

- (b) L. D. Kapoor, K. L. Handa and H. L. Abrol, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1954, **16**(5), 111.
3. (a) "The Essential Oils", E. Guenther, D. Van Nostrand. Co. Inc., New York, vol. I, 1948, 236 and 360; vol. VI, 1952, 151.
- (b) Gildemeister & Hoffmann's—"Die Atherischen Ole", Treibs, W. Berlin Akademie Verlag, Band IV, 1956, 602-4.
4. (a) *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, **52**, 3734; 1956, **50**, 5579d.
- (b) Tsunematsu Takemoto and Tadashi Nakajima, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1957, **77**, 1157.
5. "The Terpenes", J, L. Simonsen, and W. C. J. Ross Cambridge University Press, vol. V, 1957, 321.
6. *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, **54**, 25582g, and Ref. 3(a).
7. Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural products—National Academy of Sciences, India, (Allahabad), February. 1964—Gupta and Bhatnagar.

